

A REVIEW :PHARMACOVIGILANCE SYSTEM IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES. Miss. Safina M. Makandar * Student Dr.J.J. Magdum Trusts Anil alias pintu magdum memorial pharmacy college Dharangutti Tal. Shirol Dist. Kolhapur, Maharashtra India

Abstract:-

Pharmacovigilance is a key component of drug safety regulatory processes and is paramount for ensuring the safety profile of medications used to treat patients. All participants in the healthcare system, including healthcare providers and consumers, should understand and meaningfully engage in the pharmacovigilance process; healthcare providers should integrate pharmacovigilance into everyday practice, inviting feedback from patients. This narrative review aims to give an overview of the main topics underlying pharmacovigilance and drug safety in pharmaceutical research phase after the authorization of a drug in the United States. The US Food and Drug Administration guidance and post-approval regulatory actions are considered from an industry perspective.

pharmacovigilance, the monitoring of drugs for potential risks, they safeguard the welfare of consumers of medicines. Comprehensive, documented methods for evaluating the safety of a drug during its development and its subsequent use allow identification of any risks associated with the drug's use throughout its lifetime. The comprehensive identification of safety issues associated with a drug is improved when all parties involved in the development and use of drugs participate in the pharmacovigilance process. For example, clinicians should regularly ask their patients if they are experiencing any issues with their treatment, and patients should be encouraged to report problems they encounter with a particular medication to their healthcare provider.

pharmacovigilance system in india:-

Development of pharmacovigilance system in India.

Pharmacovigilance system in australia:-

1. Pharmacovigilance System in Australia

The safety alert for thalidomide tragedy was first generated in Australia and this situation paved the path for the establishment of an Australian drug evaluation committee in 1963 by the national health department to investigate the safety of new medicines and a program for spontaneous reporting of ADRs. The Australian ADR reporting system was initiated with the sharing of reporting forms to prescribers in 1964. Australia is also one of the pioneer members of the WHO's program for International Drug Monitoring. The adverse drug reaction advisory committee was formed in 1970 in response to the increasing number of reports. In 1971 "Blue card" form was introduced for clinicians to report. Now, these cards are not physically available and doctors can report any ADR via the Australian adverse drug reporting system.

Pharmacovigilance in Australia is largely dependent on voluntary reporting by patients and Healthcare Professionals (HCPs) and mandatory reporting by the industry. The HCPs can report medicine or vaccine adverse events online or by downloading a template. The downloaded template is installed in the best practice software for reporting. Consumers can report by telephone, online and by email. The industry is required to mandatory report ADRs through online, electronic data interchange and by email. The reports are stored in the Database of Adverse Event Notifications (DAEN). It includes information related to ADRs of prescription, over-the-counter, and complementary medicines and devices . The Therapeutic Goods Administration publishes online information on medicine safety including medicines safety reviews, medicine safety guidelines, and scientific review reports. During the year 2020–2021, 57,771 medicine and vaccine adverse event reports were accepted by TGA. There is a 59% increase in reports than last year. The pharmaceutical industry submitted 14,418 (24%) during 2019–2020, 14,128 (61%) in 2020–2021 and HCPs contributed 4744 (20%) in 2019–2020, and 7960 (13%) in 2020–2021 of the total reports. Pharmacists were the toppers in sending AE (Adverse Event) reports among all HCPs .

The TGA is most interested in adverse events related to newly listed or registered drugs, medicines or vaccine interactions, not mentioned in literature or product information and events causing death or hospitalization. Following Europe, Australia has introduced the Black Triangle scheme to identify newly registered medicines and already registered drugs utilized in new ways requiring enhanced vigilance .

2.2. Pharmacovigilance System in Canada

Health Canada's post-marketing surveillance program is called Canada Vigilance Program. This program was launched in 1965 to collect the suspected ADRs of the marketed products. The ADRs in the database can be searched online . Like many other countries, there is a voluntary ADR reporting system for HCPs and consumers. Canadian Food and Drugs Act and

regulations require market authorization holders (MAHs) to report all serious ADRs related to their marketed products. The MAHs also report serious ADRs occurring in foreign countries for products being marketed in Canada. The collected ADRs are stored in Canada Vigilance online database which can be accessed for information. There are seven Canadian regional vigilance centres which serve as contact points for HCPs and consumers and send information to Canada Vigilance National Office (centralized database) . Since the beginning of the Canada vigilance program, the number of ADRs has increased annually. The contributing factors are an increase in the number of marketed products, mandatory reporting by hospitals, the industry's patient safety programs, active surveillance programs etc. Health Canada received 96,559 domestic reports in 2019 while during the last 10 years, the number of reports has increased 4 times from 22,211 reports in 2010 to 96,559 reports in 2019. In one year 93.6% of reports were from mandatory reporters while during the last 10 years, 90% of reports were from industry

Canada has shown its intent to amend the food and drug regulations and medical devices regulations in 2022. Among the various proposed amendments, there will be a requirement for a risk management plan from applicants for medicines and medical devices authorization

2.3. Pharmacovigilance System in Chile

In Chile, the concept of pharmacovigilance was first introduced in 1972 after a paper published by two researchers. The Chilean Institute of Public Health (ISP) launched the National Center for Drug and Pharmacovigilance (CENIMEF in Spanish, which is no longer official) in 1994 and developed a voluntary reporting system for suspected adverse reactions. As part of the ISP, a PV Committee was formed to analyze causality for adverse effects reported during the surveillance period, as well as an application to incorporate the centre into the WHO International Drug Surveillance Program. Chile was the fifth in South America to become a member of the Pharmacovigilance Program advocated by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Uppsala Monitoring Center (UMC) .

In 2010, Chile published its first pharmacovigilance regulations, establishing its sub-department of pharmacovigilance (SDFV) within its regulatory agency (ISP) to coordinate pharmacovigilance activities. ISP considered the approach of the EMA and other regulators during the COVID pandemic and published a technical and regulatory guide, Implementation of Pharmacovigilance for SARS-CoV-2 vaccines in Chile, in December 2020. A stimulated passive surveillance system was also implemented by the regulator in addition to this framework, which involved sending virtual surveys to patients with COVID-19 vaccinations at three points in time: 48 h after each dose (inoculation), 7 days later, and 42 days afterwards

In January 2016, hospitals in Chile's capital, Santiago, and another regional hospital reported adverse effects linked to the use of metronidazole (an antibiotic commonly used to treat bacterial and parasitic infections of the skin, mouth, and genitals). A suspicious batch of metronidazole was withdrawn from sale by the manufacturer .

2.4. Pharmacovigilance System in European Union

All EU member countries are full members of WHO PIDM . After the wake of the shocking thalidomide catastrophe, to provide signals of unexpected adverse reactions, spontaneous adverse reaction reporting schemes have been developed. European Union enacted its first Community Directive (Council Directive 65/65/EEC) on medicines in 1965 . A number of these directives provided a framework for the development of current medical systems, which are still in place today in the third millennium . The overall objectives of regulatory pharmacovigilance include monitoring long-term safety in clinical practice to detect safety hazards that had not previously been identified or to determine if adverse effect profiles have changed, taking action to improve the safety of authorized medicines by assessing their risks and benefits, giving users information about their medicines so they can use them safely and effectively, and any action should be monitored to determine its impact . In the early 1990s, EU member states began to cooperate more closely as proposals were made to build a more closely integrated regulatory system. Thus, the European Agency for Medication Product Evaluation was created in 1995. Later on, it was named as European Medicine Agency. Through cooperation with the European medicines regulatory network, EMA has achieved tremendous success—a partnership unique among the EMA, European Commission, and the medicines regulatory authorities in the European Economic Area .

The regulatory system in Europe is unique. The regulatory network is composed of the European Commission, the European Medicines Agency as well as the national competent authorities in member states of the European Economic Area (EEA). EMA's work and success are based on the European medicines regulatory network. As well as coordinating and supporting interactions between 50 national competent authorities, the Agency also supports and coordinates efforts in veterinary medicine . Scientists from across Europe participate in more than thirty EMA working groups to provide scientific expertise to regulatory processes. The regulatory pharmacovigilance in Europe has been enhanced two times in the new century. In 2004 the risk management approach was introduced through Regulation (EC) No. 726/2004 (EC, 2004) and in 2010 a new legislation was introduced in the EU area . Eudravigilance was introduced by the EMA in 2001. Eudravigilance is the European Union's system for managing and analyzing data related to suspected adverse reactions to medicines that have been approved for commercial use or are currently being studied in clinical trials. It enables the electronic transmission of individual case safety reports between all stakeholders, early identification and evaluation of potential safety signals; and product information in EEA. Since May 2004, Eudravigilance has included clinical trial data alongside case reports from around the world post-authorization. One of the EU countries, France also established a separate "French Pharmacovigilance data (FPVD)" in In 1985 .

This development conformed to the standards and formats of the International Council on Harmonization of Technical Requirements for Registration of Pharmaceuticals for Human Use

The need for pharmacovigilance regulation in the EU arose when it was estimated that ADRs accounted for 5% of hospital admissions and 197,000 annual deaths. The European Commission reviewed the European system of safety monitoring and sponsored an independent study. Pharmacovigilance regulations were implemented in 2012 in the EU

which was a revolutionary step in the field of medicine regulation . The pharmacovigilance regulations implementations brought about transparency, stakeholders' engagement, and safeguarding of public health. It also rationalized the responsibilities between the regulators and the pharmaceutical industry.

European Union has integrated pharmacovigilance at all stages of the medical life cycle. The European Union has a separate data information system for suspected ADRs called Eudravigilance. EMA has launched this database for reporting suspected ADRs of authorized medicines and the medicines being studied during clinical trials for better analysis of the safety of medicines. The market authorization holders send reports to this database and don't require sending them to NRAs. Similarly, EMA shares the information with WHO and NRAs do not need to send ICSR to vigilance. The patients and healthcare professionals send spontaneous ADR reports to NRAs. The reporting of unexpected ADRs during clinical trials will be shared with NRAs until the application of new clinical trial regulations. The public can also access the database through a separate portal .

700 million Euros was estimated as the cost of hospitalization due to avoidable ADRs in a UK-based study and the EU commission in 2008 calculated an EU-wide societal cost of ADRs 79 billion along with 197,000 deaths. EU adopted new pharmacovigilance legislation in 2010 which provides mandatory provisions to record ADRs reported by patients to MAHs and NRAs .

After a successful audit, the Eudravigilance database was declared fully functional and its system has met the functional specifications. On the recommendations of the pharmacovigilance Risk Assessment Committee (PRAC), an operational plan containing the key activities and developments for three years 2018–2020 was devised. EMA confirms that by the end of 2017, Eudravigilance contained a repository of more than 12.45 million ICSRs and 7.95 million cases along with information on 744,219 medicinal products. All ICSRs are also available to UMC.

2.5. Pharmacovigilance System in Israel

Ministry of Health Israel created a Pharmacovigilance and Drug Information Department in 2012 within the Pharmaceutical Division. Israel has gone through a drug-related tragedy in 2011 commonly called a "levothyroxine event". The drug was being marketed since 1981 and the company changed its composition. The adverse drug reactions associated with new formulations were noticed by many HCPs. Before this, there was no requirement for MAHs to report any ADRs to the Ministry of Health . An investigation after the event revealed similar changes in formulations in Denmark in 2006 and New Zealand in 2007. Many adverse events were also reported as a result of these changes. The MAH was not able to transfer this vital PV information to the Israeli Ministry of Health on time, preventing the Ministry from taking preventive measures .

As a result of an amendment to the Pharmacists Regulations (Medical Products) 1986 in June 2013, all MAHs, and health maintenance organizations (HMOs) in Israel are now required to report ADRs and new safety information to the Ministry of Health. Swissmedic and the FDA

are two leading medicine agencies with which Israel has signed agreements. Sharing of PV data is part of these memoranda of understanding. The total number of signals identified between 2014 and 2016 is 850 . Israel's Ministry of Health is taking a giant step toward international standards with its recent requirement that the pharmaceutical industry implements Risk Management Plans (RMPs) for product classifications that are considered high-risk .

2.6. Pharmacovigilance System in Japan

Japan kicked off the pharmacovigilance activities in 1967 from the selected medical institutions. In 1972 it became a member of WHO's program for international drug monitoring (UMC) . Japan established a post-marketing system in 1979 to assess the safety and efficacy of marketed medicines. Japan is considered the first country in the world which mandated pharmaceutical companies to require carrying out pharmacovigilance activities by establishing three systems i.e., the ADR collection and reporting system, the re-examination system, and the re-evaluation system. Pharmacies were included in this program in 1984 and from 1997 all pharmacies have joined the program. Good post-marketing surveillance system practice was introduced in 1993. In 2004 this program was divided under the revised pharmaceutical affairs law into good vigilance practice and good post-marketing study practice. Japan is considered one of the largest medicine markets in Asia. HCPs are legally required to report any suspected ADRs since 2003

2.7. Pharmacovigilance System in New Zealand

New Zealand started the pharmacovigilance program in 1965 and was among 10 countries that founded the WHO's program for international drug monitoring. A separate unit named MedSafe is established in the Ministry of Health under DG Health to collect and review the safety reports of marketed products by the market authorization holders. The collection of suspected ADRs is contracted by the Ministry of Health to the centre for adverse reaction monitoring (CARM). The CARM is established in the Department of Preventive and Social Medicine at the University of Otago, Dunedin. Both MedSafe and CARM work closely on the reports and if need regulatory action is taken by the MedSafe. There is a Medicines Adverse Reactions Committee (MARC) to advise the Minister of Health on the safety of approved medicines .

The CARM contains a database of 110,000 reports which contains a large chunk from the HCPs. Pharmaceutical companies and patients also contribute to ADR reports significantly. In New Zealand, adverse reactions to medicines have been reported at the highest rate per capita for the last two decades.

Healthcare professionals can report ADRs online, with ADR reporting software, free post-yellow cards and a mobile application. There is an enhanced vigilance scheme for certain medicines to provide more information for investigating signal detection called M2 monitoring.

2.8. Pharmacovigilance System in Saudi Arabia

As an independent agency, the Saudi Food and Drug Authority (SFDA) was set up in 2003 to ensure the safety of foods, drugs, medical devices and biological substances. Within the drug sector is the Vigilance and Benefit-Risk Assessment (VBRA) executive directorate. Since the NPC was launched in 2009, Saudi Arabia has been a full member of the WHO-UMC 2009, becoming the 92nd country to have done so. An EU GVP was adopted by the SFDA in 2015 (which was published in 2012), and an SFDA GVP was published that same year, becoming effective in 2016. The third version of the guidelines is published on 14 November 2022. A second Saudi Pharmacovigilance Guidelines on Good Pharmacovigilance Practices (GVP) was released in 2015 by the Saudi Food and Drug Authority. SFDA safety alerts, guidelines on adverse drug event reporting by healthcare professionals and an information list on the safety of various brands are available on the website.

Healthcare providers and consumers/patients can submit online and paper forms, ADRs and quality defect reports, and the SFDA accept communications via the internet, mail, e-mail, fax, and phone. As part of its assessment of marketed medications' safety, the VBRA evaluates ADRs and conducts data mining and signal detection based on these reports. There is an independent Pharmacovigilance committee that reviews drug profiles, comprising pharmacists, physicians, drug safety experts, and epidemiologists. In addition, since the Saudi GVP and the GVP for Arab countries are both based on the EU GVP, there are some minor variations, such as the ICSR submission requirements and the PSUR requirements for generics.

2.9. Pharmacovigilance System in the United Kingdom (UK)

After the thalidomide disaster, a committee on the safety of medicines (CSM) was established by the United Kingdom (UK). In 1965 yellow card scheme was introduced in the UK and the chairman of the CSM communicated to all HCPs especially doctors and dentists to report any unexpected reactions. The suspected ADRs can be reported online or on the yellow card mobile application. Several safety alerts were generated from information received via yellow cards. The pharmaceutical industry is legally required to report the ADRs. A black triangle (▼) is displayed on the label and a summary of product characteristics of new medicines and vaccines that are under additional monitoring. All ADRs are reported for such products. MHRA minimize the risk by taking regulatory actions in the form of product information changes. Package label restricting the indications, changes from OTC to prescription medicines and publications in the drug safety updates.

Pharmacovigilance system in UK

2.10. Pharmacovigilance System in the USA

The US federal food, drugs and cosmetics Act was established in 1938 in aftermath of the sulfanilamide elixir (Diethyl glycol) tragedy which killed 107 people in 1937. The marketing authorization holders were required to demonstrate the safety of medicines before launching them into the market. The thalidomide tragedy in 1960 further creates an environment to strengthen the safety monitoring regulations. This time manufacturers were required to prove the efficacy of the medicines. The USA was among the first ten pioneering members of the WHO's PIDM in 1968.

Usually, American patients are the first to receive the new drug molecules hence the chances of experiencing ADRs are also predominantly increased in the US population. The US pharmacovigilance system also faces the challenge of early detection of safety issues

Among the FDA divisions, the Center for Drug Evaluation and Research (CDER) is responsible for approving and regulating drugs, the Center for Biologics Evaluation and Research (CBER) for biological products, the Center for Devices and Radiological Health (CDRH) for medical devices for human use. Office of surveillance and epidemiology works under CDER. FDA has 10 teams of safety evaluators' mostly clinical pharmacists. The spontaneous ADR reporting by patients, consumers and healthcare professionals through MedWatch is voluntary. The MedWatch forms 3500A and 3500B are used for reporting ADRs by the HCPs, consumers and industry. ADR reporting by the manufacturers is mandatory. The majority of the ADRs are from manufacturers which constitute 95% of the total reports received by the FDA. All ADR reports are sent to the central database FDA Adverse Event Reporting System (FAERS). The system contains more than 9 million reports since 1969. The FDA's CFR title 21 contains various sections including the ones that encompass the safety requirements for medicines and medical devices for human use. The 21 CFR, 314.80 requires that post-marketing safety reports must be submitted to the FDA within 15 days from all domestic and foreign sources and periodic ADEs reports as per schedule. When any safety concern comes to the surface by FAERS then further evaluation is done extending to more studies using the large databases. Any such record is maintained for ten years. Vaccine Adverse Event Reporting System (VAERS) is separately provided for the public to report ADEs/AEFI related to vaccines (<https://vaers.hhs.gov/reportevent.html>, accessed on 22 July 2022). WONDER, an online database is utilized for inquiries regarding vaccine adverse events. A number of useful guidelines for the industry have been provided including E2E Pharmacovigilance Planning Guidance, Post-marketing Studies and Clinical Trials Guidance, and good pharmacovigilance practices. US follows the ICH guidelines being the founding member. The US does not require a qualified person for the pharmacovigilance and pharmacovigilance system master file

2.11. Pharmacovigilance System in Uruguay

The pharmacovigilance activities were started in Uruguay in the year 2000 . The Pharmacovigilance Unit was created in 2006 in the ministry of Health Uruguay. By adopting Good Pharmacovigilance Practices for the Americas (WHO), this Unit collaborates with its National Advisory Committee, formed the same year, and provides technical assistance. Members include members of the university (Faculty of Medicine, Faculty of Chemistry), members of the public health system, and others. Uruguay became a member of the WHO PIDM in 2001 . Pharmacovigilance is included in the course of Pharmaceutical Care and it is also incorporated in some post-graduate courses.

As a result of Ministerial Ordinance No. 292, the additional surveillance modality has been added to the National Pharmacovigilance System as an intermediate step between passive (spontaneous reports) and active (intensive) pharmacovigilance. 12 December 2014, Ordinance No. 798. Additional surveillance will apply to medicines that contain a new active ingredient, biotechnological medicines, or those for which data regarding post-authorization is required. The Department of Medicine will define which medicines are covered by this additional surveillance modality Uruguay has given a priority to patient safety in dentistry as well and established an online ADR reporting system for dental products

CONCLUSION:-

Pharmacovigilance is a part of healthcare system worldwide .The WHO leads Pharamacovigilance operations and provides technical support in reporting ADRs. Many countries have well-built pharmacovigilance systems , but actual incidence of ADRs is much higher than what is reported underreporting of ADRs is a major problem as well as the quality of reports . the basic objective of pharmacovigilance is the safe use of drugs , patient safety , and ultimately safeguarding public health . To achive this goal , national regulators and international organization should empower healthcare professionals and the public report

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Introduction:-

Pharmacovigilance is highly regulated in the major regions of the world where medicines are developed. European Medicines Agency (EMA), Food and Drug Administration (FDA), and Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices Agency (PMDA) are the major regulatory agencies driving global pharmacovigilance regulations. Legislation, regulations, guidance, and guidelines are established to define the department's organizational structure, individual roles and systems, as well as to develop the skills necessary to perform pharmacovigilance efficiently. The Code of Federal Regulations in the USA, as well as national laws and ordinances in Europe, are legally binding [1]. Through collaboration between the World Health Organization, the Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS) and the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH), pharmacovigilance has evolved into a regulatory activity [2]. There are three internationally recognized pharmacovigilance systems: the European Union (EU) pharmacovigilance system, the WHO Uppsala Monitoring Center system, and the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) system.

***Advantages of pharmacovigilance:-**

Improve patient care

safety in relation to the use of medicines

Methods that are systematic, automated, and workable for filtering enormous datasets

The World Health Organization (WHO), the FDA, and other organizations' extensive safety databases should be used more effectively.

Focusing pharmacovigilance efforts on important reporting relationships to increase efficiency

Improved decision-making capabilities for the pharmaceutical sector and regulators

***Drawbacks of pharmacovigilance:-**

any unwanted medical occurrence in a patient who has been given a pharmaceutical product that may or may not have been caused by treatment with the product.

may cause complications of a disease or procedure and negatively affect its prognosis.

aims to describe the safety profile of the drug, i.e., the potential risks and missing information